

Follicular Flushing in Iraqis' Poor Responders and It's Effect on Number of Oocyte and Number of Embryos and Grading during Oocytes Retrieval in ICSI

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Abstract

Background: In assisted reproductive technique treatments, follicular flushing is a technique used during oocyte retrieval. The goal of oocyte retrieval is to maximize the number of oocytes recovered. It does not appear to improve outcomes in normal-responding patients. Several studies have shown that in poor responders a low oocyte count reduces the rate of pregnancy; an additional oocyte should therefore substantially increase the chances of success. **Aim of study:** To investigate the impacts of follicular flushing on the number of oocytes and number of embryos and grading during oocytes retrieval in intracytoplasmic sperm injection. **Patient and methods:** An interventional comparative study that was conducted for a period of 18 months from February 2023 till August 2024. It included 40 infertile females who attended the infertility consultation room and diagnosed as poor responders with normal male analysis. They were divided into two groups: Group A included 20 women underwent follicular flushing following aspiration and group B included 20 women underwent follicular aspiration alone. The outcome evaluated were the number of oocytes retrieved and number and grading of embryos. **Results:** Patients in group A had a significantly higher number of oocytes retrieved and lower MII oocytes, MI oocytes, and number of injected embryos compared with group B. **Conclusion:** Follicular flushing may enhance the retrieval of oocytes in poor responders, maximizing the chances of successful fertilization.

Introduction

Infertility, defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as the failure to conceive after one year of unprotected, regular sexual intercourse, affects nearly 10% of the global population and is recognized as the fifth leading serious global disability among young people [1,2]. The increasing delay in childbearing and the growing incidence of male infertility contribute to its rising prevalence. Notably, age is among the most influential factors affecting female fertility, with significant declines in ovarian reserve occurring after the age of 35 [1]. WHO classifies infertility into primary

and secondary types. Primary infertility refers to women who have never conceived despite two years of exposure to pregnancy, with prevalence rates ranging from 5.7% to 26.4% globally, while secondary infertility involves the inability to conceive again following a previous natural pregnancy [3,4]. Female infertility alone affects an estimated 48 million women worldwide, with the highest burden in South Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa, and the Middle East [5,28]. Causes of infertility are multifactorial and include ovulatory dysfunction, tubal pathology, uterine anomalies, endometriosis, and unexplained infertility. Ovulatory

More Information

How to cite this article: Hussein NH, Al Khafajy ZH, Abdulhameed WA, Abd NA. Follicular Flushing in Iraqis' Poor Responders and It's Effect on Number of Oocyte and Number of Embryos and Grading during Oocytes Retrieval in ICSI. Eur J Med Health Res, 2025;3(4):96-101.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(4).17

Keywords:

Infertility,
ICSI,
flushing,
follicular,
poor responders.

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disorders, especially polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), account for approximately 25% of female infertility cases and are often linked to disruptions in the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis, hyperandrogenism, and metabolic abnormalities [6,7]. Tubal factors, such as those resulting from pelvic inflammatory disease or hydrosalpinges, are also significant contributors, as they interfere with oocyte transport and fertilization [8,9]. As assisted reproductive technologies (ART) such as intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI) evolve, optimizing oocyte retrieval techniques becomes increasingly important to enhance fertilization and pregnancy outcomes. Oocyte retrieval, typically performed 34–36 hours after hCG administration, is a pivotal step in ART [10,11]. One technique employed to improve oocyte yield during retrieval is follicular flushing, particularly in women with poor ovarian response. This method involves injecting culture media into the follicle after aspiration to retrieve residual oocytes [12]. Although early studies suggested increased oocyte yield with multiple flushes (up to 97% after four flushes), recent evidence questions its routine use, citing prolonged procedure time and minimal benefit in normal responders [13]. Nevertheless, in patients with low ovarian reserve or poor response, maximizing the oocyte yield is essential, as even a single additional oocyte can significantly impact the chances of successful fertilization and embryo development [14]. This study aims to investigate the effects of follicular flushing on the number of retrieved oocytes, embryos formed, and their quality during ICSI cycles.

Method

This interventional study was conducted over an 18-month period, from February 2023 to August 2024, at the Al-Najaf Infertility and Andrology Center. Ethical approval was obtained from the center’s administration, and verbal consent was secured from each participant. Patient confidentiality was maintained by replacing names with coded identifiers and storing data securely. The study involved 40 infertile women diagnosed as poor ovarian responders based on the Bologna criteria, which requires at least two of the following: maternal age ≥40 years or other risk factors for poor response, a previous poor response (≤3 oocytes in a prior stimulation), or an abnormal ovarian reserve (AFC <7 follicles or AMH <1.1 ng/mL) [15,29]. All participants had partners with normal

semen parameters. After obtaining informed written consent, participants were randomly divided into two groups. Group A (n=20) underwent follicular aspiration with flushing using a double-lumen needle, while Group B (n=20) underwent aspiration alone. Randomization was based on assigning odd and even numbers sequentially. All participants received controlled ovarian stimulation via a fixed antagonist protocol. Cetrotide (0.25 mg) was administered beginning on day 2 of the cycle. Gonadotropin dosing (FSH alone or in combination with HMG) was tailored based on ovarian response monitored by transvaginal ultrasound on days 2, 5, 7, 9, and 11. Triggering was done with either 5,000 or 10,000 IU of hCG once at least one dominant follicle ≥17 mm or two follicles ≥16 mm were present. Oocyte retrieval occurred 35 hours post-trigger using a 17-gauge double-lumen needle under 140 mmHg pressure at 37°C. Collected oocytes were classified as GV, M1, M2, or abnormal. Only M2 and selected M1 oocytes underwent ICSI. Embryo development was assessed on days 1, 3, and 5. The main outcome measures were the number of oocytes retrieved and the number and quality of embryos formed. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 26. Continuous variables were analyzed using the independent t-test, and categorical variables using the Chi-square test. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

This study included a total of 40 infertile women regarded as poor responders. They were randomly assigned to either follicular flushing following aspiration (Group A included 20 patients) or follicular aspiration alone (Group B included 20 patients). The mean age in group A was 30.81 ± 4.60 years, and 10 women (50%) were < 30 years. In group B, the mean age was 32.10 ± 6.25 years, and 9 (45%) aged ≥ 35 years. Regarding infertility, the highest proportion of the studied patients had primary infertility, 16 (80%) in group A and 14 (70%) in group B. The most common duration of infertility was 5 – 9 years in 11 patients (55%) of group A and 10 (50%) of group B. Thirteen (65%) and 11 (55%) of the husbands in groups A and B were ≥ 35 years, respectively. Both groups had comparable sociodemographic and disease-related characteristics, and there was no significant difference (P ≥ 0.05) between them regarding women's age, husband's age, type of infertility, and duration of infertility (Table 1).

Table 1: Sociodemographic and Disease-Related Characteristics of the Study Groups

Patients’ characteristics	Study groups		P - Value
	A (%) (n= 20)	B (%) (n= 20)	
Female age (Years)			
< 30	10 (50.0)	8 (40.0)	0.09
30 – 34	7 (35.0)	3 (15.0)	

≥ 35	3 (15.0)	9 (45.0)	
Type of Infertility			
Primary	16 (80.0)	14 (70.0)	0.465
Secondary	4 (20.0)	6 (30.0)	
Duration of infertility (years)			
1 - 4	4 (20.0)	6 (30.0)	0.756
5 - 9	11 (55.0)	10 (50.0)	
≥ 10	5 (25.0)	4 (20.0)	
Husbands age (Years)			
< 35	7 (35.0)	9 (45.0)	0.519
≥ 35	13 (65.0)	11 (55.0)	

According to seminal fluid analysis, the mean sperm volume was 2.44 ml in group A vs. 2.92 ml in group B. Group A had a slightly lower sperm count than group B (94.3 million/ml vs. 96.8 million/ml). Immobility was lower in group A than in group B (53.2% vs. 57.1%). Sperm concentration was 28.2 million/ml in group A vs. 34.5 million/ml in group B. Group B had a slightly higher morphology (52.1%) than group A (49.5%) as illustrated in (Figure 1).

The comparison between the two groups according to baseline hormones showed no statistically significant difference ($P \geq 0.05$) between the two groups in consideration of mean levels of FSH, LH, estradiol, prolactin, AMH, and TSH as shown in (Table 2).

Figure 1: Distribution of the Study Groups According to Seminal Fluid Analysis

Table 2: Comparison of Baseline Hormones between the Study Groups

Basal hormonal Profile	Study groups		P – Value
	A - Mean ± SD	B - Mean ± SD	
FSH (mIU/mL)	8.27 ± 2.36	8.89 ± 2.59	0.443
LH (mIU/mL)	5.34 ± 2.06	6.58 ± 2.78	0.377
Estradiol (pg/mL)	39.22 ± 8.98	40.43 ± 9.03	0.257
Prolactin (ng/mL)	18.82 ± 6.78	17.24 ± 5.49	0.649
AMH (ng/mL)	0.85 ± 0.37	1.07 ± 0.67	0.523
TSH (mIU/mL)	1.84 ± 0.55	1.98 ± 0.69	0.316

Table 3: Comparison of Clinical Parameters and Embryological Outcomes between the Studied Groups

Clinical Parameter	Study groups		P - Value
	A - Mean ± SD	B - Mean ± SD	
Number of oocytes retrieved	8.95 ± 3.92	5.09 ± 2.43	0.003
Number of MII oocyte	3.10 ± 1.02	5.65 ± 2.67	0.031
Number of MI oocyte	1.19 ± 0.32	3.76 ± 1.09	0.001
Number of GV oocyte	1.80 ± 0.83	2.06 ± 1.03	0.563
Number of injected embryos	3.12 ± 1.07	5.45 ± 2.37	0.035
Embryo day 1	2.31 ± 1.08	3.80 ± 1.34	0.057
Embryo day 2	2.22 ± 1.06	3.55 ± 1.27	0.11
Embryo day 3	2.28 ± 1.20	2.76 ± 1.15	0.523
Embryo transfer	1.51 ± 0.94	1.55 ± 1.04	0.846

The comparison of clinical parameters and embryological outcome between the two groups

revealed a statistically significant difference in the number of oocytes retrieved, MII oocytes, MI oocytes,

and number of injected embryos. Patients in group A had a significantly higher number of oocytes retrieved (8.95 vs. 5.09, $P = 0.003$) and lower MII oocytes (3.10 vs. 5.65, $P = 0.031$), MI oocytes (1.19 vs. 3.76, $P = 0.001$), and number of injected embryos (3.12 vs. 5.45, $P = 0.035$) compared with group B. On the other hand, we found no evidence of a significant difference ($P \geq 0.05$) in the germinal vesicle oocytes, number of embryos on days 1, 2, and 3, and number of transferred embryos as illustrated in (Table 3) and (Figure 2).

The comparison of human menopausal gonadotropin 75 (HMG 75) injection and antral follicle count (AFC) between the two groups showed that the mean values of both HMG 75 injection and AFC were higher in group B than in group A; however, the difference was not statistically significant ($P \geq 0.05$) as illustrated in (Table 4).

Figure 2: Mean Levels of Clinical Parameters and Embryological Outcomes that Significantly Different between the Two Groups

Table 4: Comparison of Human Menopausal Gonadotropin 75 Injection and Antral Follicle Count between the Studied Groups

Variable	Study groups		P - Value
	A - Mean ± SD	B - Mean ± SD	
HMG 75 injection	330 ± 85.68	345 ± 90.19	0.652
AFC	5.25 ± 1.06	5.30 ± 1.30	0.895

Discussion

Assisted reproductive technology (ART), particularly intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI), relies heavily on the retrieval of mature, competent oocytes to achieve successful fertilization and embryo development. Follicular flushing has been proposed as a strategy to improve oocyte yield, particularly in poor ovarian responders, where each additional oocyte retrieved may significantly increase the chance of successful pregnancy [16,17]. The present study investigated the impact of follicular flushing on oocyte and embryo outcomes in a cohort of 40 infertile women diagnosed as poor responders, and found that although the total number of retrieved oocytes was significantly higher in the flushing group, no significant improvement was observed in terms of mature oocytes (MII), embryo quality, or embryo transfer outcomes. The absence of significant differences in baseline characteristics, including age, type and duration of infertility, BMI, and hormonal profiles, between the two groups supports the internal validity of this study. These findings are consistent with earlier studies by Von Horn et al. and Calabre et al., which also showed no significant differences in patient demographics and hormonal profiles between flush and non-flush groups [18,19]. While hormonal levels such as FSH, LH, estradiol, and AMH are essential in predicting ovarian reserve and response, mechanical interventions like flushing are not expected to affect systemic hormone levels acutely [20,21]. Our findings align partially with those from Xiao et al. and Neyens et al., who reported increased oocyte

retrieval rates with flushing without compromising embryo quality or pregnancy outcomes [17,22]. Similarly, Aydin et al. noted improved oocyte yields with up to three flushes in poor responders [23]. However, contrasting evidence from Haydardedeoglu et al. and Martini et al. suggested that follicular flushing might result in fewer MII oocytes and does not improve overall outcomes, emphasizing its time-consuming nature and limited benefit in poor responders [23,24]. These discrepancies may be attributed to differences in stimulation protocols, needle gauge, aspiration pressure, and number of flushes performed [25]. Moreover, this study found no significant difference in the antral follicle count (AFC) or HMG 75 injection requirements between groups, although both were slightly higher in the non-flush group. A low AFC, a marker of poor ovarian reserve, may inherently limit the effectiveness of follicular flushing due to fewer retrievable follicles [26]. Likewise, gonadotropin resistance and suboptimal response to hMG in poor responders may further reduce stimulation efficacy [25]. Despite some potential in select cases, current evidence supports a more individualized approach to follicular flushing, especially considering the added procedural time and uncertain benefit in embryo yield and quality [27].

Conclusion

Follicular flushing may enhance the retrieval of oocytes in poor responders, maximizing the chances of successful fertilization. While the number of oocytes retrieved in Group A was higher, they had lower counts

of mature oocytes (MII) when compared to Group B. This implies that while more oocytes can be retrieved, the quality of oocytes may vary. The findings underscore the complexity in managing poor responders, indicating that tailored approaches based on hormonal profiles and ovarian response are necessary to maximize ART outcomes.

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